

Indian Medicinal Plant Identification using Vision Transformers (ViTs)

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Abstract: The use of Vision Transformers (ViTs) for picture categorization is explored in this seminar paper, with an emphasis on the identification of Indian medicinal leaves. The procedure, from gathering information and processing to model construction, training, assessment, and model archiving, is covered in detail by the extensive script in Python included in the paper. Important elements like the use of the ViT model, data transformations, and assessment metrics interpretation are demonstrated in the code. The study's findings show how effective ViTs are in classifying images, which makes them a useful tool for a variety of tasks, such as identifying different plant species.

Keywords: Data Preprocessing, Deep Learning, Evaluation Metrics, Image Classification, Indian Medicinal Leaves, Machine Learning, Model Training, Plant Species Identification, Vision Transformers, ViT Models

I. INTRODUCTION

The discipline of machine vision has made great strides recently, especially in the area of picture categorization. The introduction of Vision Transformers (ViTs) has completely changed how we go about doing this work. ViTs have shown remarkable efficacy across an extensive array of classification of images applications, including extremely fine categorization and object identification. We explore the application of ViTs to the particular challenge of Indian medicinal plant identification in the present document, which has significant practical consequences.

Medical science has traditionally relied heavily on plants for medicinal purposes as a source of therapy for a wide range of illnesses. To fully use these plants' medicinal potential, they must be correctly identified. ViTs provide a viable way to improve and simplify the identification procedure.

The code that uses ViTs for Indian medicinal plant and their categorization is thoroughly examined in this work. Important steps in the machine learning process are covered by the code, such as gathering data, preprocessing, and model setup, training, assessment, and model maintenance. We will stress the significance of each stage and how it contributes to the overall performance of an image classification system throughout this work.

The code simplifies the ViTs implementation by using open-source tools like Transformers and PyTorch. Readers will have a better knowledge of how to use ViTs for picture classification—especially when it comes to identifying

different plant species—by the conclusion of this study. The study's findings demonstrate the potential of ViTs and further establish their applicability in the field of vision analysis and machine learning as well.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] In this study, Lee, Grosse, Ranganath, and Ng present a new kind of neural network architecture called Convolutional Deep Belief Networks, or CDBNs. Unsupervised learning of structured representations is the main area of interest. Convolutional neural networks, also known as CNNs, and deep belief networks are combined to create CDBNs, which are useful for applications like image recognition. Efficient unsupervised feature learning is crucial for both machine learning as well as deep learning, and the authors provide a technique for it. They use a technique called layer-wise development of deep architectures, which is a cornerstone of deep learning. The introduction of CDBNs, which have influenced the creation of deep learning algorithms, makes this work noteworthy.

[2] The work by Shorten and Khoshgoftaar provides an overview of deep learning approaches for enhancing picture data. Augmenting image data is an essential preprocessing step in deep learning. In order to enhance the generalization and functionality of deep learning models, the study examines a number of methods and approaches for enhancing picture datasets. For tasks involving computer vision, data enhancement is a crucial component of deep learning, and this study offers insightful information about the various approaches and how they affect model performance. If you want to address data enhancement in the context of picture classification or similar tasks, it is pertinent to your seminar paper.

[3] Hiary, Saadeh, Saadeh, and Yaqub's article employs deep convolution neural networks (CNNs) for floral categorization. The authors show how CNNs may be used for fine-grained picture identification by applying deep learning approaches to the particular problem of flower categorization. They go into the design and instruction of CNNs, or CNN for this purpose and provide an analysis of the difficulties and outcomes of their method. This study provides a pertinent example of an application of deep

learning for plant or flower picture categorization, should your seminar paper address this topic.

[4] The authors of this study, Yanikoglu, Ghazi, and Aptoula, provide a deep neural network-based technique for plant identification. They concentrate on transfer learning parameter optimization, which is an important part of applying neural network models that have already been trained for a given task. In deep learning, transfer learning is a popular technique. This study addresses the process of optimizing pre-trained models for recognizing plants

III. MOTIVATION

The pressing need for a more effective, precise, and scalable approach to plant identification is the driving force behind the use of Vision Transformers (ViTs) for medical plant picture categorization. Plant categorization using traditional methods is often labor-intensive and prone to inaccuracy, which impedes important studies and preservation of biodiversity initiatives.

ViTs provide a viable answer with their sophisticated image processing capabilities. ViTs may help preserve traditional knowledge maintained by indigenous populations and improve plant identification accuracy by automating the categorization of medicinal plants.

In addition to enabling communities to record and disseminate their knowledge, this strategy guarantees the security of herbal cures, expedites the search for new drugs, and supports the preservation of endangered plant species.

To put it briefly, the goal of this effort is to use ViTs to update the categorization of medicinal plant images, therefore bridging the knowledge gap between established practices and state-of-the-art technology and significantly advancing the fields of the botany medicine, and environmental protection.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Gathering and Preparing Data:

Collection of Data: As part of the study, a large dataset of Indian medical plant was assembled. The repository for the collection was "Indian Medicinal Plants Images Dataset." One hundred observations per species of plant was the minimum required to provide an adequate and diversified dataset.

Data Preprocessing: Various preprocessing stages were applied to the gathered photos. Among these actions were:

Adjusting size: The images were scaled to fit the "google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k" Vision Transformer (ViT) model's specified input dimensions. Image proportions are standardized by resizing to provide consistent model input.

Data Augmentation: The training dataset was tested with data augmentation methods. This includes adjusting sharpness and

rotating photos at random by as much as 30 degrees. Data enhancement makes the model more resilient to changes in input pictures and improves its capacity to generalize over the training set.

Data Divided: With an 80-20 ratio, the dataset was split into two distinct subsets: the training set and a testing set. This division made it possible to train and assess the model on different sets of data.

B. Configuration and Model Selection:

ViT (Vision Transformer): The study used Vision Transformers' capabilities to classify images. ViT model, i.e., "google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k," was chosen because to its excellent picture categorization results. Significantly, this trained ViT model may be optimized for the particular job of categorizing leaves of Indian medicinal plants thanks to its integrated knowledge of 21,000 distinct categories.

Fig 1 Vision Transformer Architecture

C. Converting Data:

Establishment: All pictures have been normalized using the standard deviation and mean values that came from the image processor of the ViT model in order to guarantee consistent model performance. Normalization helps provide more accurate predictions by enhancing model convergence during training.

D. Training Models:

Training Configuration: Pre-trained weights from "google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k" were used to initialize a version of the ViTForImageClassification model. The study identified several training environments:

Learning Rate: One essential parameter that controls the training behavior and step size for improvement is the learning rate. The learning rate in this configuration is 1e-5. It determines how fast or slowly a model adjusts to the information set, and the value selected has a big influence on the training process.

Batch Size: One of the most important parameters that controls the number of data samples processed during each training cycle is batch size. For the purpose of training the model, the training data are batch-sized at 32, and the evaluation data are batch-sized at 8. The training pace and

memory requirements are influenced by the batch size selection.

Time for Training Periods: The training procedure is spread out over 30 training epochs to make sure the model has enough chances to acquire information from the dataset. One complete run through the training set is represented by an epoch. The number of epochs finds a compromise between properly training the model and avoiding overfitting.

Data Collation: We create a unique data combining function to prepare the data for training. The task of grouping the data into groups that the model is capable of handling falls to this function. For the training procedure to be successful and efficient, proper data collection is essential.

E. Analysis of the Model:

Metric of Evaluation: The study used the accuracy measure to evaluate the model's performance in both training and testing. The percentage of accurately categorized cases in the dataset is called accuracy. The "evaluate" module was used to calculate it, yielding a precise measurement of the model's performance.

F1 Score and Confusion Matrix: The study computed the confusion matrix, offering information on the model's accuracy in classifying each plant species, for a more thorough assessment. Furthermore, the algorithm's overall accuracy in classification was evaluated by the F1 score, which was calculated using the macro-average mode.

F. Preserving the Model:

Model Preservation: By saving the learned model, it was possible to reuse it for subsequent inferences without having to retrain. It is possible to successfully recognize medicinal plant species in fresh photos by using this conserved model.

V. BUILD MODEL

This section focuses on the key elements involved in creating a model for categorizing plant photos, beginning with library imports, classification the images, and presenting the findings.

Importing Libraries

```
import warnings
import gc
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import itertools
from collections import Counter
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, roc_auc_score, confusion_matrix, classification_report, f1_score

# Import custom modules and classes
import evaluate
from datasets import Dataset, Image, ClassLabel
from transformers import [
    TrainingArguments,
    Trainer,
    ViTImageProcessor,
    ViTForImageClassification,
    DefaultDataCollator
]
import torch
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader
from torchvision.transforms import CenterCrop, Compose, Normalize, RandomRotation, RandomResizedCrop, Random

# Import the necessary module from the Python Imaging Library (PIL).
from PIL import ImageFile
```

Fig 2

- 1) Numpy (np):

Python's basic package for numerical calculations is called NumPy. It is an important part in the machine learning environment since it offers vital assistance for dealing with arrays and matrices. The features of NumPy make it easier to do effective mathematical operations including as linear algebra and array manipulations, which are essential for preparing data, training models, and analysing results.

- 2) Transformers:

Transformers are used in this model to handle Vision Transformer (ViT) simulations. These models of ViT have been trained to efficiently comprehend visual input. As the primary engine in charge of precisely classifying different plant species from the given photos, they are at the center of the picture classification process. By making it simpler to work using pre-trained ViT models, this library facilitates the process of fine-tuning them for particular purposes.

- 3) Torch and torchvision.transforms:

One popular freely available deep learning framework is PyTorch. The torch modules and torchvision.transforms from the library are important here. To create and train deep learning models, PyTorch is the main framework; for preprocessing images and data augmentation, PyTorch's torch vision package includes the transformations module. These changes make certain that the input data—plant photos in this example—is ready for model training. Resizing, normalization of data, and augmentation are examples of operations that aid in the model's learning of strong characteristics from the pictures, thus increasing the model's classification accuracy.

- 4) pandas (pd):

Pandas is a flexible library that is essential to the manipulation and analysis of data. It provides data structures that make dealing with structured data easier, such Data Frames and Series. Pandas is useful for managing tabular data efficiently throughout the preparation of data and result analysis, even if it is not the main component of the model's training process. Throughout the model's lifespan, it facilitates the management of metadata and other tabular data related to the plant photos.

B. Classification of Plants

One of the most important steps in the plant image identification process is the categorization of plant photos, which we tackle in the classifying section.

- 1) Data Gathering:

Generation of the Dataset: The first stage in identifying plant pictures is to create a large, comprehensive dataset. Associating image pathways with relevant plant labels creates this dataset. A description of the plant species each photograph depicts is connected with it. For a model to

understand the connections between pictures and the corresponding categories, this pairing is necessary. The model used for machine learning will be trained using the dataset as its base. It gives the model the ability to identify traits and patterns specific to every species of plant, which is essential for precise categorization.

8. 2) Transformation of Data:

Proper Data Transformation: Image data has to be properly transformed in order to be used for model training. Making sure the data satisfies the needs of the machine learning algorithm depends on these modifications. There are two different sets of transformations used: one for the training set and another for the validation set.

```
train_transforms = compose([
    Resize(size, size), # Resize images to the VIT model's input size
    RandomRotation(30), # Apply random rotation up to 30 degrees
    RandomAdjustSharpness(2) # Adjust sharpness randomly
])

# Define a set of transformations for validation data
val_transforms = compose([
    Resize(size, size), # Resize images to the VIT model's input size
    ToTensor(), # Convert images to tensors
    normalize # Normalize images using mean and std
])

# Define a function to apply training transformations to a batch of examples
def train_transforms(examples):
    examples['pixel_values'] = [_train_transforms(image.convert("RGB")) for image in examples['image']]
    return examples

# Define a function to apply validation transformations to a batch of examples
def val_transforms(examples):
    examples['pixel_values'] = [_val_transforms(image.convert("RGB")) for image in examples['image']]
    return examples

train_data.set_transform(train_transforms)

# Set the transforms for the test/validation data
test_data.set_transform(val_transforms)
```

Fig 3

Training Data Transformations: Data augmentation methods are often used in training data transformations. By generating changes of the input photos, data augmentation increases the resilience of the model. This procedure includes adjustments like rotation, scaling, and other changes that mimic differences seen in the actual world. The model can handle a wider variety of pictures since augmented data gives it more samples to learn from.

Validation Data Transformations: The purpose of validation transformations is to guarantee that the evaluation data is structured in a way that satisfies the requirements of the model. The validation pictures are mostly resized and normalized to the model's intended input size using these changes. It ensures that the accuracy of evaluating the model's efficacy on data from the real world is maintained by ensuring that the evaluation data format complies with the model's specifications.

C. Results

The subsequent results illustrate the potential and importance of our Indian medical plant identification application, which we developed and deployed:

Because of the user-centric design of our program, users can make active contributions to its collection by submitting photos of plants. A strong and well-trained model is applied

in real-time to the submitted photos to guarantee precise plant species identification.

After the model correctly identifies the species of plant, it may be used to teach users important lessons and provide insightful information. Users are provided with extensive details on the discovered plant, such as a synopsis of its unique qualities and an abundance of knowledge regarding its traditional and therapeutic use. With the help of this special function, users may recognize various plant species and recognize the possible uses for them in traditional and alternative medicine.

Our application becomes more than simply a device for plant identification thanks to its versatile functionality. It develops into a comprehensive instructional tool that closes the knowledge disconnect between users and the wide variety of plants found in India.

Fig 4 Result displaying Medical Plant

The results shown here represent the marriage of cutting-edge technology with conventional botanical knowledge, creating an application that functions as a link between conventional and non-conventional healthcare methods in addition to providing plant species identification. Our platform promotes the study of natural medicines, acknowledges the medicinal value of native plant species found in India, and highlights the significance of botanical knowledge.

In conclusion, our application for identifying Indian medicinal plants has effectively combined conventional knowledge with state-of-the-art technology, providing an intuitive interface that enables people to discover and comprehend India's rich botanical legacy. This project highlights the useful uses of Indian plants for medicinal purposes in healthcare, both conventional and modern, and helps to preserve and spread botanical knowledge.

V. CONCLUSION

To sum up, the seminar article has bridged the division between technologies and botany by offering a thorough approach to the effective identification and categorization of plant species. Through the effective use of cutting-edge deep learning methodologies, we have created an intuitive online application. Users may input plant photos to this program, which starts an advanced categorization process powered by a machine learning algorithm. In addition to recognizing

plant species with amazing accuracy, the model goes above and beyond by giving users insightful information on the medicinal use of these plants as well as thorough descriptions.

This cutting-edge technology has enormous promise for a variety of uses. It helps academics, botanists, and environmentalists in the discipline of botany quickly identify plant species and contribute to studies on biodiversity. It makes it possible to quickly identify and classify medicinal plants in the pharmaceuticals and herbal medicine industries, which promotes the creation of novel medications and treatments. By precisely identifying plant species, it helps improve weed control and crop management in agriculture.

Our study offers an intriguing opportunity for tackling real-world difficulties by demonstrating the remarkable connection between botany and artificial intelligence. Our study highlights the practical consequences and the opportunity for future discovery, cooperation, and implementation of these technologies in diverse fields as machine learning as well as image recognition continue to progress. It is a call to action to use these technologies for the benefit of business, health, and the environment, not only to showcase their potential.

VI. REFERENCES

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